

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP PIPES MADE BY MULTI FILAMENT WINDING METHOD (MFW)

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we studied the mechanical properties of CFRP pipes made by Multi Filament Winding method (MFW). Many CFRP products are made with uni-direction pre-impregnation (or “prepreg”) carbon fiber and made by sheet winding method (SW). But SW dose not put high tension to fibers. Therefore meander of carbon fibers and seam of prepreg decrease mechanical properties of pipes.

In order to solve these problems, we investigated new method ‘Multi-Filament Winding’. MFW can make seamless and meanderless pipes by its continuous winding system and putting tension to prepreg carbon tows. The seamless and meanderless structure is expected higher strength and stiffness than existing CFRP pipes made by SW. Two types of specimens were made with eight prepreg carbon tows (bobbins), four sets layers of ± 45 degree fiber orientation angle, and winding tensions were 2.1×10^{-4} N / filament and 4.2×10^{-4} N / filament. MFW CFRP pipes with 4.2×10^{-4} N / filament winding tension showed 11% higher torsional strength and 25% higher torsional stiffness than those with 2.1×10^{-4} N / filament winding tension. In addition, MFW CFRP pipes with 2.8×10^{-3} N/filament winding tension showed 8% higher torsional strength and 6% higher torsional stiffness than SW pipes. It was made clear that MFW method putting tension to prepreg carbon tows has a high potential of mechanical properties in comparison with SW.

1. Introduction

From automobiles to airplanes and so on, carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) materials are used in a wide range of applications, and these applications have been rapidly expanding as a result of active research and development in recent years. Various methods exist for the fabrication of CFRP and each has its own distinctive characteristics. Different fabrication methods are adopted according to the desired application, depending on whether, for example, there is a need for high strength/rigidity or high productivity and so forth. The CFRP used as frame material in various structural parts, such as automobile propeller shafts and industrial robot arms, are often in the form of hollow cylinders (pipes),

and the method employed in their fabrication is usually either the “filament winding (FW) method” or the “braiding (BR) method.” However, both of these methods necessarily involve undulations in the carbon fiber, called “crimp.” Crimp is a concern in the fabrication process, as its presence generally has the effect of degrading the strength of the CFRP. For this reason, the “multi-filament winding (MFW) method” has been proposed as a possible method for fabricating CFRP without producing crimp, resulting in a structure unaffected by the aforementioned degradation in strength.¹⁾

At the same time, conventional wisdom maintains that the fabrication method that ensures the highest level of strength and rigidity is the “sheet winding (SW) method,” a method that utilizes pre-impregnation (or “prepreg”) carbon fiber. The SW method involves impregnating carbon fiber with resin, forming it into semi-cured sheets and wrapping these around a mandrel that serves as a mold to form the CFRP into the desired shape. Unlike FW or BR, this fabrication method does not produce crimp, resulting in CFRP that features higher strength. However, seams will form between these prepreg carbon fiber sheets, and these seams are prone to becoming failure points. Additionally, in order to prevent gaps from forming between these prepreg carbon fiber sheets, it is necessary to wind them so that they partially overlap. This point of overlap creates a deviation in thickness, called a “spine,” that causes the resultant CFRP pipe to become asymmetrical. Further, because the carbon fiber is in a state that is free of tensile load, it features poor directional homogeneity, meaning that the carbon fiber is not fully exerting its innate strength.

In recent years, there has been a growing demand for CFRP pipes that are lightweight but feature high strength and rigidity. However, as none of the aforementioned fabrication methods adequately fulfill all of these demands, there is a clear need for a new fabrication method that can achieve further improvements in the strength and rigidity of CFRP pipes. Thus, we hypothesized that, by binding the carbon fiber in a way that applies a tensile load to the non-crimp structure of the MFW method, it would be possible to fabricate CFRP with higher strength than CFRP fabricated using the SW method with prepreg sheets. In this research, we have developed CFRP pipes that are fabricated using the MFW method and formed while applying a tensile load to the carbon fiber with the aim of fabricating CFRP with strength that is superior to CFRP fabricated using the SW method with prepreg sheets.

1-1. Sheet Winding Fabrication Method (SW)

SW is an excellent fabrication method in terms of strength and rigidity. As depicted in Figure 1, sheets of carbon fiber that have been impregnated with epoxy resin are cut to the specified fiber angle and then wrapped around a mandrel to form the carbon fiber into the desired shape. This is the most effective method for producing molded carbon fiber that features high strength and rigidity. However, when producing hollow molded forms, such as pipes, seams form between these sheets, and these seams can become failure points

1-2. Multi-Filament Winding Method (MFW)

The MFW method used in this research is depicted in the schematic diagrams in Figures 2 and 3. In this method, the carbon fiber is layered to produce a laminate structure in which a layer composed entirely of carbon fiber wound in the $+\theta$ direction is overlaid with a layer composed entirely of carbon fiber wound in the $-\theta$ direction and so forth. Wrapping multiple filaments of carbon fiber around the mandrel simultaneously eliminates the crimp that is seen in the BR method, thus forming what is called a “non-crimp structure.” This method also applies a tensile load to each filament of carbon fiber, resulting in improved fiber directionality and adhesion between fibers, as well as improved adhesion between layers of fiber.

1-3. Effects of Applying Tensile Load to Carbon Fiber on the Mechanical Properties of Pipes

The direction of the applied force load and the direction of the fiber have a significant effect on the mechanical properties of CFRP. Fibers arranged parallel to the longitudinal direction of the mandrel (0° layers) deeply affect the mechanical properties on bending deformation (Figure 4). Fibers arranged perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of the mandrel deeply affect them on lateral compressive deformation (Figure 5). Meanwhile, carbon fibers arranged at a 45° angle to the longitudinal direction of the mandrel (45° layers) affect them on torsional deformation (Figure 6).

For this report, we have fabricated CFRP pipes composed entirely of 45° layers, as this is the most facile structure to fabricate using the MFW method. We then performed torsion tests and bending tests in order to examine the effects of tensile load on the mechanical properties of the carbon fiber to which it is applied.

2. Experimentation Using Simple Stacking Sequence

2.1 Experimental Procedure

Using the MFW method, we fabricated CFRP pipe specimens with a non-crimp structure and with a tensile load applied to the carbon fiber and then measured their torsional strength and torsional rigidity. For comparison purposes, we fabricated two different types of CFRP pipe specimens with varying levels of tensile load applied to the carbon fiber using the MFW method and then measured the respective torsional strength and torsional rigidity of each.

The tow prepreg carbon fiber used to fabricate the MFW pipe specimens for these experiments was Torayca T800SC, manufactured by Toray Industries, Inc. The epoxy resin used was SX3, manufactured by JX Nippon Oil & Energy Corporation, and the resin content was 30wt% of the carbon fiber. Two different specimens were fabricated with varying levels of tensile load applied to the carbon fiber. The fabricated specimens were each composed of four layers of prepreg carbon fiber at the following respective fiber angles: +45° / -45° / +45° / -45°. The MFW machine used was a filament winding machine manufactured by Murata Machinery, Ltd. Table 1 lists the inner diameter and outer diameter of each pipe specimen and the tensile load applied to each filament of carbon fiber. The tensile load applied to each filament of carbon fiber was calculated by dividing the total tensile load applied to the tow prepreg carbon fiber by the total number of filaments present.

In addition, we also fabricated CFRP pipe specimens using the SW method, a method that is generally considered to ensure high strength and rigidity, for comparison with the MFW method. The prepreg carbon fiber used in the CFRP pipe specimens produced using the SW method was PYROFIL MRX350E100S, a thermosetting type of prepreg carbon fiber manufactured by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. featuring the same tensile modulus of elasticity (30t) as the prepreg carbon fiber used in the CFRP pipe specimens produced using the MFW method.

Because the weight differential between the MFW pipe specimens and the SW pipe specimens affects their respective torsional strength, for our evaluations, we divided the total torsional strength by the total weight to calculate the torsional strength by weight. We likewise performed comparative evaluations of the rigidity of the respective pipe specimens.

Table 1. Simple Stacking Sequence Specimen List

	MFW1	MFW2	SW1
Stacking Sequence	+45°/-45°/+45°/-45°		
Length (mm)	400	400	400
Weight (g)	25.3	25.7	19.1
Inner Diameter (mm)	13.2	13.2	13.2
Outer Diameter (mm)	15.04	15.08	14.64
Fiber Tension (N/Filament)	2.1×10^{-4}	4.2×10^{-4}	-

2-2. Testing Methodology

Torsion Test Methodology

The methodology employed in the torsion tests is depicted in Figure 7. Each pipe specimen was attached to two fixtures located 50mm from each end of the specimen so that the span between the fixtures was 300mm and the specimen was anchored in place. The fixture on one end of the specimen was then rotated at a speed of 2.0rpm in order to apply torsional force to the specimens. In this report, torsional strength refers to the maximum torque exerted at the time of failure of each pipe specimen.

Bending Test Methodology

The methodology employed in the bending tests is depicted in Figure 8. Each pipe specimen was placed on two supports spaced 300mm apart and a force load was applied to the exact midpoint between the supports using a load nose. In this report, bending strength refers to the maximum force

load exerted at the time of failure of each pipe specimen.

2-3. Test Results

The results of the torsion tests are indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Simple Stacking Sequence Torsion Test Results

	MFW1	MFW2	SW1
Fiber Tension (N/Filament)	2.1×10^{-4}	4.2×10^{-4}	-
Torque (Nm)	52.7	58.7	60
Torque /Angle (Nm/deg)	3.1	3.9	2.8
Torque / Weight (Nm/g)	2.08	2.28	3.13
Torque / Angle / Weight (Nm/deg/g)	0.12	0.15	0.15

The results of the torsion tests performed on MFW1 and MFW2 indicate that increasing the tensile load applied to the carbon fiber increases both the torsional strength and torsional rigidity of the resultant CFRP pipe. However, comparing the results for SW1 with the results for MFW2, which was the MFW specimen with the higher tensile load applied to the carbon fiber, we found that MFW2 falls short of SW1 in terms of torsional strength and fails to exceed SW1 in terms of torsional rigidity. In other words, these results suggest that the tensile load applied in MFW2 was insufficient and that, in order to achieve tensile properties that are superior to those produced by SW, it is necessary to apply further tensile load to the carbon fiber.

3. Experimentation Using Complex Stacking Sequence

In our examination of MFW pipes with simple stacking sequences, we found that, while increasing the tensile load applied to the carbon fiber results in increased torsional strength and torsional rigidity, the MFW pipe specimens that we tested were nonetheless inferior to the SW pipe specimens. In other words, in order to increase the torsional strength and torsional rigidity of MFW pipes to a level that exceeds the tensile properties of SW pipes, it is necessary to further increase the tensile load applied to the carbon fiber. Thus, having learned that applying a tensile load to the carbon fiber improves the carbon fiber's tensile properties, we next performed tests to compare SW pipe specimens with MFW/SW hybrid pipe specimens featuring complex stacking sequences with multiple fiber angles, a configuration that more closely approximates the actual specifications for CFRP pipes. Further, because such mechanical properties as bending strength and bending rigidity are also important in the actual usage of CFRP pipes, we also performed bending tests this time.

3-1. Experimental Procedures

The tow prepreg carbon fiber used to fabricate the MFW layers of the hybrid pipe specimens for these experiments was Torayca T800SC, manufactured by Toray Industries, Inc. The epoxy resin used was SX3, manufactured by JX Nippon Oil & Energy Corporation, and the resin content was 30wt% of the carbon fiber. The fabricated specimens were each composed of seven layers of prepreg carbon fiber at the following respective fiber angles: $+45^\circ / -45^\circ / 0^\circ / 90^\circ / 0^\circ / 90^\circ / 0^\circ$. Here, only the $+45^\circ$ and -45° layers were formed using the MFW method; all other layers were fabricated using the SW method and prepreg carbon fiber manufactured by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. (MRX350E100S), which is equivalent to the prepreg carbon fiber used in the layers of the pipe specimens that were fabricated using the MFW method. The tensile load applied per carbon filament in the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers fabricated using the MFW method was the highest possible tensile load that could be applied with our existing equipment before the carbon fiber filaments snapped.

In addition, we also fabricated entirely SW pipe specimens for comparison using only the prepreg carbon fiber manufactured by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. (MRX350E100S). The torsion tests and three-point bending tests were conducted according to the same test methodology described in (2-2). Table 3 lists the specifications of the CFRP pipe specimens that were used in these tests.

Table 3. Complex Stacking Sequence Specimen List

	MFW3	SW2
Stacking Sequence	+45°/-45°/0°/90°/0°/90°/0°	
Length (mm)	400	400
Weight (g)	19.0	19.4
Inner Diameter (mm)	13.2	13.2
Outer Diameter (mm)	14.58	14.55
Fiber Tension (N/Filament)	2.8×10^{-3}	-

3-2. Test Results and Observations

The results of the torsion tests are indicated in Table 4. Further, because such mechanical properties as bending strength and bending rigidity are also important in the actual usage of CFRP pipes, we also performed bending tests, the results of which are indicated in Table 5.

Table 4. Complex Stacking Sequence Torsion Test Results

	MFW3	SW2
Fiber Tension (N/Filament)	2.8×10^{-3}	-
Torque (Nm)	51.2	47.3
Torque / Angle (Nm/deg)	1.05	0.99
Torque / Weight (Nm/g)	2.70	2.44
Torque / Angle / Weight (Nm/deg/g)	0.55	0.51

From our comparison of MFW3 and SW2, we found that it is possible to achieve torsional strength and torsional rigidity that are superior to the tensile properties produced by SW by increasing the tensile load applied to the carbon fiber. Cross sections of the MFW/SW hybrid pipe specimen and the SW pipe specimens can be seen in Figures 9(a) and 9(b), respectively. We can see in these images that, while there are no microscopic voids between the 45° MFW layers, several microscopic voids are extant between the 45° SW layers. It can be surmised that, because the 45° MFW layers were formed with a tensile load applied to the carbon fiber, voids within the carbon fiber have been pushed outward, increasing the adhesion between fibers and thereby improving torsional strength and torsional rigidity.

Table 5. Complex Stacking Sequence Three-Point Bending Test Results

	MFW3	SW2
Fiber Tension (N/Filament)	2.8×10^{-3}	-
Strength (N)	1165.4	1107.6
Stiffness (N/mm)	76.1	78.0
Strength / Weight (N/g)	56.11	57.07
Stiffness / Weight (N/mm/g)	4.01	4.02

Based on the results of the three-point bending test, even after increasing the tensile load applied to the carbon fiber, MFW3 does not show any advantage over SW in terms of three-point bending strength. As described in (1-3), it can be surmised that, because the 45° layers deform in a direction that is other than the direction of the tensile load applied to the carbon fiber during bending deformation, the tensile load does not have an appreciable effect on bending strength or rigidity.

4. Conclusions

In this research, we have developed CFRP pipes that are fabricated using the MFW method and formed while applying a tensile load to the carbon fiber. As a result, we were able to verify that the use of the MFW method results in a non-crimp structure and that, by applying a tensile load to the carbon fiber, it is possible to produce CFRP pipes with tensile properties that are superior to those produced using SW, which is generally considered to be a fabrication method that produces CFRP

with high strength and rigidity. In our examination, we performed tests and evaluations in which only the 45° layers were fabricated using the MFW method. However, we believe that there is potential for similar improvements in the mechanical properties of CFRP pipes in which the 90° layers, 0° layers and layers at other fiber angles are also fabricated using the MFW method. In the future, we intend to examine other fiber angles in our continuing research.

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Figure 1. SW Method Schematic Diagram

Figure 2. MFW Method Schematic Diagram (Overall Drawing)

Figure 3. MFW Method Schematic Diagram (45° Layers)

Figure 4. Direction of Force Load Applied to Carbon Fiber during Bending Deformation

Figure 5. Direction of Force Load Applied to Carbon Fiber during Compressive Deformation

Figure 6. Direction of Force Load Applied to Carbon Fiber during Torsional Deformation

Figure 7. Torsion Test

Figure 8. Three-Point Bending Test

Figure 9. MFW3, SW2 Cross-Sectional Photographs